

**A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE TALENT MANAGEMENT
ALAGENDRA SPINNING MILL PRIVATE LIMITED
MADURAI DISTRICT: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY**

P. Madhanagopu*, V. Tamilselvi & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of MBA, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

These days organization's talent is its primary source of competitive advantage. Performance of organization depends upon performance of its employees. If employees of an organization possess unique competence, that will differentiate them from their competitors. In this competitive environment retention of talented workforce is a major task for HR managers along with acquisition. Talent management is a very complex and critical task. Right Talent acquisition makes organization strategy more strong. The current global economic situation has increased overall job-seekers in employment market worldwide, but there is still notable talent shortage in different sectors and different countries, this leads to increase the problem of "Talent Mismatch." As today's corporate world requires a person with multitasking skill, talent acquisition is becoming very difficult. As a result, finding the "right" person for a particular job is becoming more challenging. Not only acquisition even retention of talented workforce has become greatest challenge for organization. Today's changing landscape of business requires its HR to act more strategically to build employee engagement which is a great tool for talent management. Talent Management focuses on how individuals enter; move up across or out of the organization. Talent Management will succeed with the support of strong organization structure.

About Alagendra Spinning Mill:

Welcome to the traditional world of Alagendra Textiles Limited. We have created our own wonderful universe of yarns with exclusive count range of 100% cotton carded yarn. Alagendra textiles Limited was incorporated in the year 1997 and has registered office in Madurai and factory at Theni. The company has been working profitably since inception with its team of dedicated staff whose striving effort has placed the company on the top. The principal activity of the company is to manufacture hank & cone of 20s, 30s and 40s single and double 100 % cotton ring spun yarn. The Company aims to increase its global market presence by diversifying into value added areas of superfine carded yarns. Expansion in capacity is in progress. We offer strong and long continuous length of yarns which helps to create eye catchy textiles and designer fabrics. We are also an importer of raw cotton, procured mainly from established suppliers based in many parts of the world. Cotton (*Gossypium Hirsutum*) is a natural fiber of great economic importance as a raw material for the textile industry. The word cotton is derived from the Arabic word? *Quan?* Which was often used by the Arab traders. Archaeologists have found that in Egypt cotton was used to make textile fabrics at least 7000 years ago. Successful cultivation of cotton requires a long growing season, plenty of water and sunshine, with dry weather for the harvest. In general these conditions are met in warm sub- tropical latitudes in the northern and southern hemisphere.

Purpose of Talent Management:

Talent management is a key succession planning tool that provides an integrated means of identifying, selecting, developing, and retaining top talent within our organization which is required for long term planning. Talent management provides a means of, Accelerating the development of employees by identifying opportunities for career growth & development within the organization. Identifying internal talent pools and transferring knowledge to others within the organization.

Benefits of Talent Management:

- Talent management is integral to modern businesses and is one of crucial management functions in an organization. Here we have listed down the benefits that talent management has to offer
- It helps the organization fulfil its vision with the help of efficient and promising talented people.
- Talent management also assists the organizations to build a talent pool comprising a list of talented people to meet future exigencies.
- It makes the organizations more competitive and progressive

- It paves the way for future leadership.
- It helps automate the core processes and helps capture data for making better decisions.
- Automates repetitive tasks like creating salaries thereby releasing time and resources for making strategies and more critical decisions.

Objectives of the Study:

- To know the extent of importance of talent management projects
- To understand the level of impact of talent management provided in retaining employees
- To know about the impact of talent management in the performance of the employee
- To know the attraction and development practices in talent management

Review of Literature:

Hitu (2019) in this study intended to explore the talent management scenario in the textile company. The major revelations from the study were, Textile Company is more interested in identifying the right talent, and developing and retaining it but whereas public banks are covering up with their job security, pension support. The study did not attempt to know the employee perspective about talent management and its relevance in both sectors of textile.

Rehman and Humayoun (2020) found out that talent management has a positive impact on the attitude of the employees and the organizational performance. They also concluded that organizations which want to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors need to take effective measures to manage their talent pool. He cited that organizations need to formulate an effective talent management strategy to effectively manage and retain the talent and should always consider it one of the most important functions to grow in the dynamic business conditions.

Mohamadzadeh (2020) studied the impact of talent management on the organizational productivity and success. For any organization, in order to grow, effective talent management is necessary. It is very essential to hire talented resources because with their help only the organizations are able to gain a competitive edge in the market. He expressed that in the era of globalization and immense cut-throat competition, talent management has become the need of the hour. The organizations therefore should understand their core competencies if they want to overpower their competitors.

Rehman and Humayoun (2020) Empirical Study of Talent Management Program and Its Impact on the Employee's Retention and Performance in the textile industry. *Human Resource Management Research*, 61-70.

Hanif and Yunfei (2021) cited those different practices related to talent management play an important role for motivating and therefore retaining the talent in the organization. Different human resource functions like recruitments, training, performance management, succession planning etc. play a major role in the incorporation of effective talent management practices. The successful implementation of these strategies related to talent management has a tremendous positive impact on the business outcomes of any company and on the productivity and efficiency of its employee performance as well.

Mani (2021) It is found that the effectiveness of talent management practices factors in a textile company in a particular area is moderate, that means the impact of talent management practices factors like job-related factors, recruitment & selection factors, training & appraisal factors and employee key factors is just above average level. When the difference of effectiveness of talent management practices among public sector banks and private sector banks are examined, it is found that there is no difference between the effectiveness of the talent management practices factors among the textile company.

Statement of the Problem:

Since employee reactions towards talent management should have an impact not only on the effectiveness of talent programs, but also on attitudes and culture within the unit, research in this area is important since it may provide useful information on how talent management programs should be designed to be successful. Since professional development forms an integral part of talent management, no matter what the specific definition of the concept is, it is considered important to investigate employee attitudes towards these practices. This is an attempt to find out the level of satisfaction observed by the workers' skill of the company regarding the Employee Skill Gap Analysis. The analysis and findings will be useful to improve the training development to the workers enforced by the firm. The analyses add to the general feeling of satisfaction with the company and reduce employee's turnover.

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Hypothesis of the Study:

According to Lundberg, "A hypothesis is a tentative generalization, the validity of which remains to be tested. In its most elementary stage, the hypothesis may be any hunch, guess, imaginative idea, which becomes the basis for action or investigation". A hypothesis is a prediction, almost always a prediction about the

relationship between variables. It is a statement of the researcher "s expectation or prediction about relationship among study variables. The researcher questions identify the study concepts and ask how the concepts might be related a hypothesis is the predicted answer. Hypothesis of the project the hypothesis set for the study is

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In it we study the various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying his research problem along with the logic behind them. It is necessary for the researcher to know not only the research methods techniques but also the methodology.

Data Sources:

- Primary Data: Primary data are those, which are collected for the first time. They are original in character. The data collected by the investigator for the first time for their own use is usually classed as primary data.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data are those that have already been collected by others. These are usually available in journals, periodicals, dailies, research publication official records etc., they may either be available in published form or in an unpublished form. When it is not possible to collect the data by primary method, the investigator may make use of this method

Statistical Tools Applied:

Statistical tools like simple percentage and chi square used in the compilation and computation of data.

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square Test
- Correlation Analysis

The primary data had was collected from the samples from various areas and have been properly arranged, edited and tabulated in a systematic format and analyzed by using appropriate statistical tools. A bipartite correlation and liner regression analysis were carryout using SPSS

Limitations of the Study:

- Due to time constraint, the researcher has covered only a sample of 100.
- Employees are hesitating to express their problems about the management system as they feel that performance management system is a management issue and is not ready to give opinion against management is the biggest limitation for the study.
- Most of the employees are overload with work and don't find time to spend in filling up the questionnaire.
- Due to lack of time interview schedules could not be used to collect data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: The Level of Knowledge and Talent Gained By the Training Program

S.No	Knowledge & Talent	No. of Responds	Percentage
1	High	45	45%
2	Neutral	30	30%
3	Low	25	25%
Total		100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table shows that, 45% of the respondents gained high-level knowledge and talent by the training program, and 30% gained Neutral level of knowledge and talent by the training program, 25% of the respondents gained low the level of knowledge and talent by the training program,

Table 2: Transparency Regarding Talent Management

S.No	Response	No. of Responds	Percentage
1	Extremely Transparent	27	27%
2	Transparent	26	26%
3	Neutral	21	21%
4	No Transparency	26	26%
Total		100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table shows that 27% of the respondents agree that talent management is extremely transparent. for 26% of the respondents is transparent. For 21% of the respondents is neutral. For 26% of the respondents is no transparency

Conclusion:

Talent Management for the HR Community is an opportunity for HR professionals to develop in their areas of expertise and in their careers. A strong HR Community helps create a strong public service. The goal of talent management is to better understand our people in the HR Community so we can support professional and career development and align individual needs and goals with the business focus of HR. This first broad sweep of the Community provides a foundation on which to ensure leadership continuity, knowledge transfer and service continuity.

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